

Faik Pasha Cami

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Faik Paşa Cami is a mosque in Arta modern day Epirus in North Western Greece. It is known as "imaret", indicating the presence of an Ottoman tekke in the region.

Date Range: 1449 CE - 1460 CE

Region: Marathovouni Arta

Region tags: Mediterranean Sea, Greece, Balkans, Arta

The region under examination is a settlement on the outskirts of the city of Arta, next to river Arachthos. It was conquered by the Ottomans in the 19th century and was annexed by the Kingdom of Greece in two phases: in 1881 and in 1913. The mosque under examination was converted to a church.

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

General Variables

The society in which the religious place is located is best characterized as (please choose one):

– A state

Reasons for Creation/Construction/Consecration

Is the place used for the worship of/communication with non-human supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Dedicated to more than one supernatural being:

– No

↳ Dedicated to a supernatural being:

– Yes [specify]

Is the place used for the worship of a semi-divine human being:

– No

Is the place used for the worship of non-divine ancestors:

– No

Were the structures built by specific groups of people:

– Yes

↳ Groups:

– Men

Was the place created as the result of an event:

– Yes

↳ Specify

– War/battle

Was the place commissioned/built by an official political entity:

A political entity is a local power structure that leverages a workforce.

– Yes

↳ Specify

– Private individual

Was the place thought to have originated as the result of divine intervention:

– No

Was the place created to mark or commemorate the birthplace of a supernatural or human being:

– No

Was the creation of the place sponsored by an external financial/material donation:

– Yes

↳ Is this sponsor of the same religious group/tradition as the main usage of the place:

– Yes

Was the establishment of the place motivated by:

– Thanksgiving to a god/gods for favor received

Was the place built specifically for housing scriptures/sacred texts:

– No

Topographical Context

Is the place associated with a feature in the landscape

– Tree, grove, or forest

– Water source

Is the place situated in an urban or significantly urbanized area:

– No

Is the place situated in a rural setting:

– Yes

Are there settlements in close proximity to the place:

– Yes

Are there routes of travel in close proximity to the place:

– Yes

Does the place involve human-made features besides structure:

Other features might be ground clearing, terracing, other modifications of the local environment.

– Yes

Type of feature

– Clearing

– Plantings

Is the place situated far removed from non-religious places of habitation:

– No

Sources and Excavations

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

– Source 1

Has this place been the focus of excavation (pre-modern, illicit, or scientific):

Answer 'Yes' for each period or type of excavation.

– No

Has this place been looted:

– Yes

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

– Source 1 URL

– Source 2 URL

– Source 2 Description

Structures Present

Are there structures or features present:

Instructions: Answer once for each structure/feature or group that can be differentiated.

– Yes

↳ A group of features:

– Yes

↳ Are they part of a single design/construction stage:

– No

↳ A single structure

– No

↳ One single feature

– Other [specify]

↳ A group of structures:

– Yes

↳ Are they part of a single design/construction stage:

– No

↳ Is it part of a larger place/sanctuary:

– Yes

↳ Is the structure/feature finished:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature intended to last beyond a generation:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature modified through time:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature destroyed:

– Yes

↳ Has the structure/feature been reconstructed:

– No

↳ What is the function of the structure/feature or group:

Answer "Yes" once for each distinct function

– Worship

↳ Worship:

– Communal

Design and Material Remains

Overall Structure

Is the place made up of multiple built structures:

– Yes

↳ Are any of the structures attached to other structures:

– Yes

↳ Is there a hierarchy among the structures:

– Yes

↳ Are any of the structures attached to or associated with a landscape feature:

– Yes

Is the structure/feature made out of human-made materials

– Yes [specify]

Is monumental architecture present:

Monumental architecture is defined here as a built structure that surpasses average human proportions and in general is larger and more complex than is necessary to fulfill the structure's utilitarian function(s). Examples of monumental architecture include Mesopotamian Ziggurats, Egyptian Pyramids, Greek and Roman temples, Mesoamerican Pyramids, North American and Aegean burial mounds, etc.

– Yes

↳ Height of largest single religious monument, meters:

– I don't know

↳ Size of average monument, square meters:

– I don't know

↳ Height of average monument, meters:

– I don't know

↳ In the average place, what percentage of area is taken up by built monuments:

– Percentage

↳ Footprint of largest single religious monument, square meters:

Please add dimensions in the comments, if known.

– I don't know

Is the structure/feature made out of natural materials:

Answer [Yes] for each material type

– Yes

↳ Earth

– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

↳ Sand

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Clay

– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– No

↳ Plaster

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– No

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– Yes

↳ Wood

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Grass

– No

↳ Stone

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Lime

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Other

– Other [specify]

Decoration

Is decoration present:

– Yes

- ↳ Are there inscriptions as part of the decoration:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Are the inscriptions informative/declarative [e.g. historical narratives, calendars, donor lists etc...]
 - Yes
 - ↳ Are the inscriptions a formal dedication:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Other [Specify]
 - Other [specify]
 - ↳ Are the inscriptions ornamental:
 - Yes
- ↳ Other type of decoration:
 - No
- ↳ Is the decoration hidden or restricted from view:
 - No
- ↳ Is decoration part of the building (permanent):
 - Yes
 - ↳ On the outside:
 - Yes
 - ↳ On the inside:
 - Yes
- ↳ Is the decoration non-figural:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Is it geometric/abstract
 - Yes

↳ Floral motifs

– Yes

↳ Is it writing/caligraphy

– Yes

↳ Other [Specify]

– Other [specify]

↳ Are there statues present:

– No

↳ Are there paintings present:

– No

↳ Are there mosaics present:

– No

↳ Is the decoration figural:

A figural representation is defined here as one that contains the depiction of discernible human, anthropomorphic, animal, or zoomorphic forms. In general, it differentiates between animate and inanimate beings, as well as between narrative compositions and still life, landscapes, abstraction, etc. Answer [Yes] for each type of figure depicted

– Yes

↳ Are there gods depicted:

– No

↳ Are there humans depicted:

– No

↳ Are there animals depicted:

– No

↳ Are there animal-human hybrids depicted:

– No

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↳ Are there other supernatural beings depicted:

– No

↳ Are there reliefs present:

A relief as opposed to sculpture carved on the round is a work of sculpture in which the figures project from a background support, generally a flat surface. Reliefs can be carved out of stone, clay, or a similar material.

– No

↳ Is decoration attached to the building, i.e. movable reliefs or tapestries

– Yes

Iconography

Are there distinct features of the iconography:

– No

Beliefs and Practices

Funerary Associations

Is this place a tomb/burial:

– Yes

Are grave goods present:

– No

Are formal burials present:

– Yes

↳ Domestic context:

Interred beneath floors of house, or in areas of domestic activity

– Yes

↳ As cenotaphs:

– Yes

↳ In cemetery:

– No

↳ Family tomb/crypt:

– No

↳ Other

– Other [specify]

Is this a place for treatment of the corpse:

– No

Is this a place for the worship of the dead:

– No

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

Co-sacrifices are animal/human sacrifices prompted by the death of the primary occupant of the tomb/burial.

– No

Supernatural Beings

Does the supreme high god communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Is a supreme high god present:

– No

Do human spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are nonhuman supernatural beings present:

– No

Do nonhuman spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are previously human spirits present:

– No

Are mixed human-divine beings present:

– No

Do mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Is the supernatural being/high god present in the form of a cult statue(s):

– Field doesn't know

Supernatural Interactions

Do visitors communicate with the gods or supernatural beings:

– I don't know

Is supernatural monitoring present:

– No

Ritual and Performance

Do rituals occur at this place:

Rituals are visibly enacted behaviors by one or more people for the purposes of religious observance.

– No

Sacrifices, Offerings, and Maintenance

Are sacrifices performed at this place:

– No

Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory:

– No

Are material offerings present:

– No

Is maintenance of the place performed:

– No

Are there self-sacrifices present:

– No

Pilgrimage and Festivals

Are pilgrimages present:

– I don't know

Is this place a venue for feasting:

– No

Are festivals present:

– Yes

Divination and Healing

Is divination present:

– No

Is healing present/practiced at this place:

– No

Institutions and Scriptures

Writing/Scriptures

Is non-religious writing stored at this place:

Economic documents, records etc.

– Yes

Are there scriptures associated with this place:

– Yes

↳ Are they oral:

– No

↳ Are they written:

– Yes

↳ Are they written at this place:

– Yes

↳ Is there a story associated with the origin and/or construction of this place:

– Yes

↳ Are there religious specialists in charge of interpreting the scriptures:

– No

↳ Are the scriptures part of the building/place:

– Yes

↳ Attached to the structures as decoration:

– Yes

↳ As dedicatory inscription(s):

– Yes

↳ Other

– Other [specify]

↳ Housed within the place/structure:

– Yes

Public Works

Does this place serve as a location for services to the community:

– No

Religious Specialists

Is this place used for the training of religious specialists:

– No

Does this place incorporate a living space for religious specialists:

– Yes

Are there formal institutions for the maintenance of the place:

Institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders

– Yes

Are religious specialists present/in charge of this place:

Religious specialists are individuals whose primary duties within a population group are not concerned with subsistence or craft production but the maintenance of the religious landscape and culture of the group.

– No

Bureaucracy

Does this place control economic resources (land, goods, tools):

– No

Is there a formal bureaucracy present at this place:

A bureaucracy consists of a hierarchical system of accounting and rule maintenance primarily concerned with material wealth.

– Yes

Is a bureaucracy present permanently:

– No

Is a bureaucracy present on a temporary or seasonal basis:

– Yes

Bibliography

General References

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